

HOME of mobile Europeans Quality Labels

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H **OME**
quality student accommodation

	LABELS	ICONS	CRITERIA	INDICATORS
1.	International friendliness		<p>Accommodation adequate to the needs of international students.</p> <p><i>A listing should qualify for all the mandatory fields, and at least one of the non-mandatory fields.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Wi-fi (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Basic furniture (bed , desk, closet, chair) (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Online booking available (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Contract translation in English available (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Short-term contract available, min. 3 month (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Communication in English ✓ International guarantor allowed
2.	Room quality		<p>Room provided with all necessary furniture</p> <p><i>A listing should qualify for 4 out of 6 indicators to get the label.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ > single bed ✓ Pillow(s) ✓ Bed linen ✓ Bath towels ✓ Desk and chair ✓ Closet/drawers

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3.	Supersecure		Accommodation providing above average safety features, including against fire accidents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Lock on room door ✓ Surveillance of the building (either video or concierge)
4.	Well-equipped kitchen		<p>Well-equipped accommodation, displaying above average kitchen appliances.</p> <p><i>A listing should qualify for all the mandatory fields, and at least 2 out of 3 non-mandatory fields.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Dishwasher ✓ Oven (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Microwave ✓ Stove (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Kitchenware
5.	Well-equipped laundry		<p>Well-equipped accommodation, displaying above average laundry appliances</p> <p><i>A listing should qualify for the mandatory field, and at least 2 out of 3 non-mandatory fields</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Washing machine (<i>mandatory</i>) ✓ Iron ✓ Iron board ✓ Drying rack

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6.	Wheelchair accessible		Accommodation entirely accessible for persons with reduced mobility and/or using a wheelchair	✓ Wheelchair accessible
7.	Premium accommodation		Accommodation providing exclusive features <i>A listing should qualify for 3 out of 5 indicators to get the label.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Sports facilities ✓ Pool ✓ Game room ✓ Surveillance of the building (either video or concierge) ✓ Cleaning service